

Low-Cost 3D Printed Rolling-Diaphragm Cylinders for Accurate Force Control

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Abstract—In this paper we present a novel torque transmission system that is employed to remotize actuators of robotic systems. The proposed system is based on rolling diaphragm cylinders and it is characterized by a very high degree of transparency. In this contribution, we show the possibility of using a common low-cost/commercial stereolithographic printer to manufacture the basic elements of the transmission and we present some of the performance of a preliminary prototype of the system.

Index Terms—Hydrostatic, Transmission, Rolling Diaphragms, 3D Printing, Stereolithography

I. INTRODUCTION

Next generation of collaborative robots are conceived to share workspace with human operators and so they have to accurately control the forces exchanged with the surrounding environment in order to ensure a safe human-machine interaction. Conventional industrial robot are conceived to be stiff and accurate in position control so they are often unsuitable to perform delicate interaction tasks, such as in manipulation of fragile objects or in safe reaction to uneven loads.

Accurate control of the interaction during dynamic operations can be achieved by dynamically transparent robots, i.e. characterised by high bandwidth and low inertia/moving masses. A strategy often used to reduce the moving masses is the remotization of actuators of the robot in order to minimize the global inertia. Remotization of actuators can be achieved in different ways and it usually characterized by a trade-off between quality of the transmission, often referred as "transparency", and complexity/cost [1], [2]. In this contribution, we illustrate a novel design solution for the delocalization of actuators of an upper-limbs rehabilitation exoskeleton (Fig. 1) that employs a *rolling diaphragms hydrostatic transmission* [3], [4]. The proposed architecture combines the efficiency of the electric motors with the high specific torque related to fluid actuation. Rolling membranes offer a solution to the traditional trade-off between leakages and sliding friction in hydraulic/pneumatic systems [5]: rolling diaphragms rolls from the cylinder to the piston surface, avoiding contact between moving parts and perfectly sealing the fluid volume. Specifically, we present a novel design for the implementation of this transmission system which further improves the quality of the transmission and makes it possible to integrate the

Fig. 1: Scheme of the remotization of actuators implemented with the proposed hydrostatic transmission system (left) and preliminary prototype 3D printed (SLA printing) elbow exoskeleton (right).

system into robotic links. Additionally, we show how the simplicity/reliability of the proposed design can be exploited to strongly reduce the production costs of the system through stereolithography (SLA) manufacturing process. SLA process features low printing costs in the range of 100 ÷ 200 €/l, comparable with other traditional additive printing techniques. This technique is versatile and can produce parts in a wide variety of resins with many different mechanical properties (with a continuous on-going improvement).

II. OPERATING PRINCIPLE

A schematic of the rolling diaphragm hydrostatic transmission (RDHT) is shown in figure 1a. The system is composed by two identical transmission joints, one *input joint* installed at the remote actuator side and one *output joint* connected to the robot joint. Each joint is composed of a pair of identical cylinders connected in antagonistic configuration through a toothed-pulley and timing belt mechanism.

The hydraulic cylinders embedded in the transmission system are based on rolling diaphragms which act as sealing of

Fig. 2: Experimental characterization of the transmission.

the cylinder fluid chamber while guaranteeing a frictionless displacement of the moving parts.

As the electric motor applies a torque T_I at the input joint, a rotation θ_I is generated at the corresponding pulley. This results in the compression (chA) of one of the two fluid lines and in the decompression of the other one (chB). The pressure variation Δp propagates through the fluid lines, so that an output torque $T_O \approx T_I = rA\Delta p$ is applied at the body connected to the output joint. r and A represent the pulleys radius and the diaphragms effective area, respectively. When an incompressible fluid is employed in the hydraulic lines, the configuration of the system can be approximately described with just one degree of freedom, so that any input rotation θ_I produces an output rotation $\theta_O \approx \theta_I$.

Since rolling diaphragms are single acting devices and cannot support reverse pressure the transmission lines need to be preloaded at a certain initial pressure p_0 to guarantee always positive pressures. In particular, the minimum pressure offset should be larger than half of the maximum working pressure within the working range.

III. EXPERIMENTAL CHARACTERIZATION

The transmission capability of reflecting the input torque T_I to the output side was assessed. A load cell was employed to measure the reaction torque T_O of the output link that was fixed to ground. The input joint was operated by a AKM52L direct drive motor from Kollmorgen with different torque intensity and frequency. Figure 2a shows the static torque-torque characteristics in a range 7 Nm, that results to be extremely accurate, precise and repeatable. The actuation system was also dynamically tested showing a force bandwidth of approximately $20 \div 30$ Hz, which is enough for the purpose of the considered application but which could be further improved by using motors or actuation system with reduced inertia. In parallel, torque tests at the nominal maximum ratings of approximately 30 Nm were successfully conducted. The *damping force* was estimated operating by hand the output joint (now free to rotate) in a range of velocities of $0 \div 2$ rad/s while the motor is applying different constant torque values. Figure 2b shows the torque exerted by the user to move the transmission. This test revealed a maximum damping torque 0.27 ± 0.08 Nm at the joint, that appears to be independent on the applied load.

Fig. 3: Stereolithography Manufacturing.

IV. STEREOLITHOGRAPHY MANUFACTURING

Additional preliminary prototypes (see Fig.3) were realized by 3D printing in order to assess the suitability of the stereolithography (SLA) manufacturing process for the production of low pressure hydraulic/pneumatic components. We employ the common/low-cost commercial *Form2* printer from *Formlabs* with standard *Grey Pro* resin (170 €/l).

The first prototype, presented in figure 3, is a standard single acting pneumatic cylinder with 50.8 mm stroke and 150 g weight. A D-137-137 rolling diaphragm from Dia-Com was embedded in this device. It was successfully tested up to 2 Bar pressure and it produced a linear force of 160 N with performance capabilities that are comparable with the results presented in the previous section.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we presented a solution for the remotization of actuators in a robotic system that feature high quality of transmission and low-cost. A preliminary prototype of the system has been developed and characterized for the actuation of 3D printed exoskeleton for arm rehabilitation. Additionally, the possibility of using additive technique to manufacture the basic components of the transmission system is demonstrated.

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